

Synthesis of Potential Amoebicides

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Several quinazoline derivatives have been synthesised as potential amoebicides.

The occurrence of quinazoline nucleus in a number of biologically active alkaloids and synthetic antipathogens has led to a wider search in this group of compounds in recent years. Several compounds, such as pyridine, pyrimidine, and quinoline derivatives, which may be regarded structurally or bio-isosterically related to quinazolines, have been found to possess pronounced antiamebic activity¹⁻⁴. This led the authors to synthesise quinazoline derivatives of type (I) with a view to testing their antiamebic activity. Should chelation be responsible for the biological activity⁵, these compounds may be expected to display it through the conformation as (II).

The required substituted-4-quinazolones were prepared by the action of formamide on 5-substituted anthranilic acids according to the modified Niementowski reaction⁶.

3-(β -Hydroxyethyl)-4-quinazolone and 6-chloro(& iodo)-3-(β -hydroxyethyl)-4-quinazolones were obtained by the condensation of the appropriately substituted 4-quinazolones with ethylene chlorohydrin. 6-Substituted 3-(β -chloroethyl)-4-quinazolones were obtained by the corresponding 3-(β -hydroxyethyl) compound with excess of thionyl chloride.

1. Waletsky *et al.*, *Science*, 1950, 111, 720; James *et al.*, *Brit. J. Pharm.*, 1952, 7, 486; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, 55, 6506.
2. Lees, *J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1951, 54, 198.
3. Conan, *Amer. J. Trop. Med.*, 1951, 31, 18; *Amer. J. Med.*, 1949, 6, 309.
4. Osbond, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1853.
5. Albert *et al.*, *Med. J. Austral.*, 1944, 31, 245; *Brit. J. Expt. Path.*, 1947, 28, 69; 1953, 34, 119.
6. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1895, 4, 51, 564.

Condensation of 6-substituted 3-(β -chloroethyl)-4-quinazolone with various amines furnished the corresponding 6-substituted 3-(β -dialkylaminoethyl)-4-quinazolone and that with piperazine provided *N,N*'-bis-(6'-substituted *N*'₃-ethylquinazolono)piperazine.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Chloroanthranilic acid was prepared according to Endicott *et al.*⁷ 5-Iodoanthranilic acid was prepared according to Wallingford *et al.*⁸ 4-Quinazolone, 6-chloro-4-quinazolone, and 6-iodo-4-quinazolone were also prepared following the method of Endicott *et al.*⁷

3-(β -Hydroxyethyl)-4-quinazolone: 6-Chloro (& Iodo)-3-(β -hydroxyethyl)-4-quinazolone.—A mixture 6-substituted 4-quinazolone(0.1*M*), ethylene chlorohydrin (0.1*M*), solid KOH(0.11*M*), and anhydrous ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 6-8 hr. After cooling, it was filtered and the solvent distilled. The residue was extracted with chloroform and the extract washed with a 5% NaOH solution. The chloroform layer was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the residue was recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

The m.p., yields, and analyses of the substituted 3-(β -hydroxyethyl)-4-quinazolones and their picrates are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
A—OH (vide structure I).

R.	Yield.	M.P.	Quinazolones.		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
			Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd..			Found.	Reqd.	
H	65	155°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	14.36	14.74	180°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₄	16.42	16.70
Cl	60	175°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	12.21	12.48	> 260°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	15.10	15.44
I	60	185°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ I	8.88	8.66	..	..	..	..

6-Substituted 3-(β -Chloroethyl)-4-quinazolone.—6-Substituted 3-(β -hydroxyethyl)-4-quinazolone (0.1*M*) was refluxed with excess of thionyl chloride(0.4*M*) for 6 hr. Excess of the latter was distilled and the residue poured on ice-cold water; sufficient potassium carbonate was added to make the mixture alkaline. The product separating was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from dilute ethanol. The m.p., yields, and analyses of substituted 3-(β -chloroethyl)-4-quinazolones and their picrates are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II
A—Cl (vide structure I).

R.	Yield.	M.P.	Quinazolones.		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
			Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.	
H	70%	120°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	13.10	13.42	160°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	15.60	16.0
Cl	70	160°	C ₁₀ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂	11.21	11.53	..	..	..	..
I	68	185°	C ₁₀ H ₈ ON ₂ ClI	8.06	8.37	..	..	..	..

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1299.

8. "Org. Synthesis", Coll. Vol. 2, 1943, p. 349.

6-Substituted 3-(β -Dialkylaminoethyl)-4-quinazolones.—A mixture of 6-substituted 3-(β -chloroethyl)-4-quinazolone (0.1M) and the secondary amine (0.4M) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 10 hr. After cooling, it was made alkaline with 5% NaOH solution, extracted with benzene, and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Dry HCl gas was then passed in this solution when the dihydrochlorides of 6-substituted 3-(β -dialkylaminoethyl)-4-quinazolones were precipitated. After filtration these were recrystallised from benzene. The m.p., yields, and analyses of the dihydrochlorides of the substituted 3-(β -dialkylaminoethyl)-4-quinazolones and their picrates are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III
(Vide structure I)

R.	Yield.	-N $\begin{matrix} R' \\ \diagdown \\ R' \end{matrix}$	Quinazolones.			Picrates.				
			M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.		
H	65%	Piperidino	180°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂	12.48	12.73	185°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₉ N ₅	17.03	17.39
H	70	Morpholino	> 280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	12.52	12.65	237°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₅	17.08	17.22
H	50	Diethyl- amino	215°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ ON ₃ Cl ₂	13.40	13.21	160°	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₉ N ₅	17.54	17.72
Cl	68	Morpholino	> 280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₃	11.20	11.48	..	..	..	..
I	65	Piperidino	> 280°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₃ ICl ₂	9.00	9.21	..	..	..	..

N₁N₄-Bis-(6'-substituted N'-ethylquinazolono)piperazine.—A mixture of 6-substituted 3-(β -chloroethyl)-4-quinazolone (0.2M), piperazine(0.10M) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25M) was refluxed in sufficient quantity of anhydrous ethanol for 8-10 hr. The mixture was cooled, filtered, and from the filtrate the solvent was distilled; the residue was recrystallised from dilute ethanol.

The m.p., yields, and analyses of N₁N₄-bis-(6'-substituted N'-ethylquinazolono)-piperazines and their picrates are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

(vide structure I)

R.	Yield.	Piperazines.			Dipicrates.				
		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.		
H	65%	280	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₆	19.14	19.53	270°	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₁₂	18.60	18.90
Cl	60	> 300°	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ Cl ₂	16.53	16.80	> 300°	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₁₂ Cl ₂	17.30	17.50
I	63	> 300°	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ I ₂	12.00	12.31	> 300°	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₁₂ I ₂	14.40	14.74